

Lorentz and Doppler metrics in Special Relativity

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The common opinion that the Lorentz transformation in Special Relativity (SR) distorts the Minkowski spacetime is false and follows from mathematically incorrect neglect of its non-orthogonality. When the non-orthogonal Lorentz transformation is properly diagonalized and expressed in the orthogonal system, the time dilation and the space distortion disappear. Consequently, the Lorentz metric produced by the Lorentz transformation is identical with the Minkowski metric. By contrast, the spacetime is distorted in the so-called Doppler metric, which is based on the ether theory and describes the Doppler shift of light in SR. The Doppler metric is Lorentz invariant and leaves the Maxwells equations unchanged from their form in the Minkowski spacetime. Consequently, the Michelson-Morley experiment and all other interferometric experiments failed to detect the ether drift, because the drift considered in the Doppler metric does not violate the Lorentz invariance. Moreover, the ether theory is supported by recent cosmological observations of the cosmic microwave background.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Lorentz transformation was introduced by Lorentz^{40,41} as an attempt to explain the null results of the Michelson-Morley experiment aimed at detecting the luminiferous ether⁴⁴. The Lorentz transformation is a linear transformation that relates two inertial coordinate systems in spacetime moving at a constant velocity v each to the other. It leaves unchanged the element of distance in the Minkowski space³⁸

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - dx^2, \quad (1)$$

implying that the speed of light c is constant in all inertial systems. This property plays a crucial role in studying light propagation problems, and the Lorentz transformation became a fundamental pillar of Special Relativity (SR) developed by Einstein in 1905¹⁷. The Lorentz factor $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-\beta^2}$ standing in the transformation between two inertial coordinate systems was interpreted in SR as a factor quantifying time dilation and length contraction characterizing the spacetime distortion of moving inertial systems.

Obviously, the assumption of the constant speed of light in all inertial systems has substantial consequences for transforming physical quantities between moving coordinate systems, including observations of the Doppler shift of photons emitted by a moving light source or observed by a moving receiver. Consequently, the classical Doppler shift is modified by multiplying by the Lorentz factor, in order to include the relativistic effects^{36,50,53}. This modification looks apparently straightforward, but it is, in fact, confusing. First, if the Lorentz transformation describes the relation between two mutually moving inertial systems, why the Doppler effect is not predicted by this transformation? Second, the apparent change of the frequency or wavelength of emitted/received waves described by the Doppler effect originates only when the source is moving relative to the observer. As a consequence, the wave speed must be different in the systems of the source and the observer in the classical theory.

If we assume no difference between the speed of light in both systems, it is questionable, whether the shift of photons can arise at all⁵⁹.

The confusion about the Doppler effect and the constant speed of light in SR is not only of the physical but also of the mathematical origin. For example, Dingle^{13,14,15} pointed to an inconsistency in the kinematical part of SR and initiated a debate of several physicists^{5,6,42} including Max Born⁴ about this topic in Nature. However, the debate was inconclusive and ended with no consensus¹⁶. Also other physicists raised some doubts about consistency of SR and the postulate of the constancy of the speed of light^{12,19,20,31,32,52,57,59}.

The aim of this paper is to clarify the relation between the Lorentz transformation and the Doppler effect, and to check whether observations of the Doppler effect are consistent with SR or not. It is shown that the formulation of SR using the Lorentz transformation is mathematically correct, but its common physical interpretation is false. This leads to self-contradictory statements and to apparent paradoxes in SR. It is shown that the null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment and other interferometric experiments does not actually mean that the speed of light must be constant in all inertial systems. Once the principle of the constancy of the speed of light is reformulated, the controversies in SR are removed.

II. THEORY

A. Coordinate transformation and metric tensor

Transformation $\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu$ from the Minkowski space with coordinates $x^\alpha = (ct, \mathbf{x}) = (ct, x, y, z)$ to a new coordinate system with coordinates $x'^\alpha = (ct', \mathbf{x}')$ = (ct', x', y', z') reads^{7,38}

$$\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu = \frac{\partial x'^\mu}{\partial x^\nu}. \quad (2)$$

Consequently, metric tensor $g'_{\alpha\beta}$ produced by transformation $\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu$ is

$$g'_{\alpha\beta} = \Lambda^\mu{}_\alpha \Lambda^\nu{}_\beta \eta_{\mu\nu}, \quad (3)$$

where $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of the Minkowski space $\eta_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(-1, +1, +1, +1)$. The distance element, $ds'^2 = g'_{\alpha\beta} dx'^\alpha dx'^\beta$, can be split into the time and space components

$$ds'^2 = -g'_{tt} c^2 dt' dt' + g'_{ii} dx'^i dx'^i, \quad (4)$$

where the Einstein summation convention over index $i = 1, 2, 3$ is applied.

Term g'_{tt} defines the time dilation and terms g'_{ii} , $i = 1, 2, 3$ define the space deformation of the metric tensor $g'_{\alpha\beta}$ with respect to the Minkowski space.

B. Lorentz transformation and Lorentz metric

Let us consider two coordinate systems x^α and x'^α moving each to the other at constant velocity v . In SR, these systems are assumed to be related by the Lorentz transformation³⁸

$$\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & -\gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ -\gamma\beta & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\beta = v/c$ is the rapidity, $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-\beta^2}$ is the Lorentz factor, velocity v is directed along the x -axis, and $\det\Lambda = 1$.

The Lorentz transformation (5) is non-orthogonal, hence the time and space coordinates are not transformed independently. This is usually overlooked and ignored. Obviously, the fact the Lorentz transformation is non-orthogonal complicates understanding the behaviour of time and space in the new coordinate system. However, using the following substitution³⁸

$$\gamma = \cosh u, \quad \gamma\beta = \sinh u, \quad (6)$$

the Lorentz transformation can be viewed as a rotation of coordinate systems, see Carroll⁷, his Eq. 1.32

$$\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \cosh u & -\sinh u & 0 & 0 \\ -\sinh u & \cosh u & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $u = \text{arctanh}\beta$, and $\det\Lambda = 1$.

This points to the fact that time and space in coordinates x'^α are rotated in the Minkowski space but they are not distorted by this transformation, see Fig. 1. When diagonalizing $\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu$ to express it in the orthogonal system, we get the unit matrix. This means that time and space are undistorted when evaluated in the system, in which time and space are independent. This is also confirmed

by calculating the Lorentz metric tensor using Eq. (3) and Eq. (5)

$$g'_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta}. \quad (8)$$

Consequently, we get

$$ds'^2 = -c^2 dt' dt' + dx'^i dx'^i. \quad (9)$$

Eq. (9) is not surprising, because the Lorentz transformation was derived under the fundamental postulate of SR that the speed of light is constant in all inertial coordinate systems. Hence, the term g'_{tt} of the metric tensor must be 1. If $g'_{tt} \neq 1$, the speed of light in the system x'^α will be varying and dependent on rapidity β .

C. Time dilation in the Lorentz metric

Using Eq. (9), we readily obtain for the time dilation in the moving coordinate system x'^α

$$\frac{dt'}{dt} = 1. \quad (10)$$

Hence, no time dilation should be observed in coordinates x'^α . This is strange and contradictory to the standard result in SR, where time is assumed to be dilated as

$$\frac{dt'}{dt} = \gamma. \quad (11)$$

The flaw in Eq. (11) originates in neglecting the fact that the Lorentz transformation is not orthogonal and the time dilation cannot be determined directly from its original form. The standard derivation of Eq. (11) found in textbooks is intuitive and mathematically incorrect in two points. First, it neglects a non-diagonal term in the first row of the Lorentz matrix in Eq. (5) to obtain Eq. (11). Second, it imposes the space contraction

$$\frac{dx'}{dx} = \frac{1}{\gamma}, \quad (12)$$

to keep the determinant of the Lorentz transformation to be 1. Hence, a diagonal form of the Lorentz matrix is commonly assumed in the form

$$(\Lambda^\mu{}_\nu)_{\text{diag}} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Consequently, the resultant Lorentz metric tensor would read from Eq. (13)

$$ds'^2 = -\gamma^2 c^2 dt' dt' + \gamma^{-2} dx' dx' + dy' dy' + dz' dz'. \quad (14)$$

The flaw of the standard derivation of the time dilation in SR is now evident: First, there is no way, how to get the Lorentz transformation in the diagonal form written in Eq. (13) from its non-diagonal form in Eq. (5).

FIG. 1. Lorentz transformation as a rotation of the coordinate system in spacetime. The length of the time axis is constant for any value of rapidity β .

Second, the metric described by Eq. (14) does not fulfil the postulate of SR about the constancy of the speed of light. Equation for the light ray along the x' -axis obeys the null geodesics, $ds'^2 = 0$, hence we get from Eq. (14)

$$\gamma^2 c^2 dt' dt' = \gamma^{-2} dx' dx' . \quad (15)$$

The contravariant speed of light C reads

$$C = \frac{dx'}{dt'} = \gamma^2 c , \quad (16)$$

and the physical speed of light \hat{C} is

$$\hat{C} = \sqrt{g_{xx}} \frac{dx'}{dt'} = \gamma c . \quad (17)$$

This implies that the Lorentz transformation itself is consistent with the SR postulate of the constant speed of light, but the derivation of the time dilation in Eq. (11) from the Lorentz transformation is flawed. Eq. (11) was derived intuitively and it is inconsistent with the Lorentz transformation as well as with the SR postulate of the constant speed of light.

D. Doppler metric and Doppler effect

Since the correctly applied Lorentz transformation predicts no time dilation, it fails to describe the Doppler effect related to the change of frequency and wavelength of photons either emitted by a moving light source or received by a moving observer. Therefore, a correct trans-

formation, called the Doppler transformation, which relates two coordinate systems moving each to the other at velocity v must be derived.

For simplicity, the light source will be at rest in coordinates x^α and the observer will recede from the source being situated at coordinates x'^α . Let us assume the Doppler transformation $D^\mu{}_\nu$ in the following form, which is a modification of the Lorentz transformation in Eq. (5)

$$D^\mu{}_\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon\gamma & -\varepsilon\gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ -\varepsilon\gamma\beta & \varepsilon\gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} , \quad (18)$$

where $\beta = v/c$ is the rapidity, $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-\beta^2}$ is the Lorentz factor, and ε is the Doppler factor which should be determined. The Doppler metric tensor $g'_{\alpha\beta}$ produced by transformation $D^\mu{}_\nu$ reads

$$g'_{\alpha\beta} = D^\mu{}_\alpha D^\nu{}_\beta \eta_{\mu\nu} , \quad (19)$$

and the distance element, $ds'^2 = g'_{\alpha\beta} dx'^\alpha dx'^\beta$, is

$$ds'^2 = -\varepsilon^2 c^2 dt' dt' + \varepsilon^2 dx' dx' + dy' dy' + dz' dz' . \quad (20)$$

Taking into account a well-known formula for the frequency shift and wavelength transformation due to the Doppler effect²¹

$$\frac{dt'}{dt} = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dx'}{dx} = \frac{1}{1-\beta} , \quad (21)$$

we readily get the Doppler factor ε in the form

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{1-\beta} . \quad (22)$$

The Doppler transformation gets the following final form

$$D^\mu{}_\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\gamma}{1-\beta} & -\frac{\gamma\beta}{1-\beta} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\gamma\beta}{1-\beta} & \frac{\gamma}{1-\beta} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

Analogously, we can derive the Doppler factor ε and the Doppler transformation $\hat{D}^\mu{}_\nu$ for an observer at rest in coordinates x^α and the source receding from the observer being situated at coordinates x'^α

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \beta, \quad (24)$$

$$\hat{D}^\mu{}_\nu = \begin{bmatrix} (1-\beta)\gamma & -(1-\beta)\gamma\beta & 0 & 0 \\ -(1-\beta)\gamma\beta & (1-\beta)\gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

E. Speed of light in Doppler metric

Equation for the light ray along the x' -axis obeys the null geodesics, $ds'^2 = 0$, hence we get from Eq. (20)

$$\varepsilon^2 c^2 dt' dt' = \varepsilon^2 dx' dx'. \quad (26)$$

The contravariant speed of light C reads

$$C = \frac{dx'}{dt'} = c, \quad (27)$$

and the physical speed of light is

$$\hat{C} = \sqrt{g_{xx}} \frac{dx'}{dt'} = \varepsilon c, \quad (28)$$

where the Doppler factor ε is defined in Eq. (22) and Eq. (24) for the case of the receding observer and receding source, respectively.

Eq. (27) implies that the Doppler transformation is consistent with the SR postulate of the constant speed of light, provided the contravariant (comoving) speed of light is considered. However, the physical (proper) speed of light is not constant, but it varies being $\hat{C} = (1-\beta)c$ for the receding observer and $\hat{C} = c/(1-\beta)$ for the receding light source. These quantities denote the relative speeds of light with respect to the moving observer or light source, respectively. Obviously, the postulate of the constancy of the physical (proper) speed of light is not valid anymore in the Doppler metrics.

F. Michelson-Morley experiments in Doppler metric

Eq. (20) shows that the Doppler metric is conformal with the Minkowski metric in the direction of motion of the coordinate systems. This means that both metrics

differ only by a scalar factor, which is common for the time and space components in the metric tensor $g_{\alpha\beta}$

$$g'_{\alpha\beta} = \Phi(x^\alpha) g_{\alpha\beta}. \quad (29)$$

The conformal transformations and metrics are intensively studied in general relativity, gravitation and cosmology^{11,22,23,26,33,55,56}. They have exceptional properties, because they are Lorentz invariant and leave the Maxwell's equations unchanged from their form in the Minkowski spacetime^{26,28,29}. Note that the Lorentz invariance is the main pillar of SR closely related to the principle of the constant speed of light³⁷.

Importantly, the Lorentz invariance of the Doppler metric implies that the light travel time measured in the Minkowski space is not changed, when the space is transformed into the Doppler metric. This applies also to all interferometric experiments with light such as the Michelson-Morley experiment^{43,44}, other ether-drift experiments^{27,34,45,46,54}, modern optical experiments with masers^{8,30} or lasers⁵¹, and experiments with optical resonator focused on testing the Lorentz invariance^{18,24,25,39,47,48,58}.

Since the above-mentioned experiments test the Lorentz invariance, they are in fact insensitive to the Doppler effect and the ether drift. It was erroneously assumed that the only Lorentz invariant systems are those with the constant physical speed of light. Instead, the experiments must give the null result for all experiments with the constant comoving speed of light. In the standard SR, the comoving and physical speeds of light are equal, hence the authors assumed that the Lorentz invariance must imply a constant physical speed of light. However, the Lorentz invariance is valid not only for the Minkowski metric but for all systems conformal with the Minkowski metric, including the Doppler metric. Therefore, the experiments could not detect the ether drift in principle. The experiments were focused on the change of the speed of light, but they ignored the apparent distortion of space associated with the Doppler effect.

III. DISCUSSION

The presented results are surprising and unexpected. Although the Lorentz transformation is mathematically correct and consistent with the postulate of SR about the constancy of the speed of light, its current physical interpretation is false. Intuitive and mathematically incorrect arguments, which ignore the non-orthogonality of the Lorentz transformation, lead to an opinion that the Lorentz transformation produces time dilation and length contraction in moving coordinate systems. Instead, the Lorentz transformation is a simple rotation transformation, which does not distort spacetime. This is proved by calculating the Lorentz transformation in its diagonal form or the Lorentz metric, which is identical with the metric of the Minkowski space.

From the physical point of view, the identity of the Minkowski and Lorentz metrics follows from the SR postulate about the constancy of the physical (proper) speed of light in all inertial systems. This condition is in a contradiction with any distortion of time. Once the time is distorted, the g_{tt} component of the metric tensor must be non-zero and the physical (proper) speed of light must vary. Hence, the condition of the constant speed of light prevents any time dilation. Moreover, it also prevents the existence of the Doppler shift of photons in moving coordinate systems. The reason is clear, if the photon is emitted from the source at velocity c and it is received by the observer at the same velocity c , no shift of the photon frequency can occur. This disproves the idea that the Doppler effect can be treated in SR by multiplying the standard Doppler formula by the Lorentz factor. This is not possible, because the Doppler shift is inherently related to the change of the physical speed of waves due to either a moving source or a moving observer. Since the Doppler shift can arise only under the varying physical speed of light, the SR postulate about the constancy of the physical speed of light should be abandoned. Instead, it should be substituted by the postulate of the constancy of the comoving speed of light. Under this postulate, the Lorentz invariance is still valid.

Since the Doppler metric is Lorentz invariant, the Michelson-Morley experiment and other ether-drift experiments had to fail to detect the ether drift. The obtained null result does not actually refute the ether hypothesis. The authors erroneously assumed that the ether drift must violate the Lorentz invariance. They ignored the fact that the Lorentz invariance is valid not only in the Minkowski metric but also in a broad class of metrics conformal with the Minkowski metric. When analysing the experimental data, the authors focused on detecting the time dilation between rays propagating at perpendicular directions but they ignored the apparent wavelength and space distortion associated with the ether drift. However, both the phenomena must be considered in proper interpretations of the experiments. The ether drift described by the Doppler metric produces an apparent time dilation as well as a wavelength distortion of photons; the two effects cancel each other and produce the null result in interferometric experiments.

Hence, the ether theory was not actually refuted by the Michelson-Morley experiments as erroneously assumed. On the contrary, recent cosmological observations of the evolution of the Universe indicate the presence of a preferred reference system called the cosmological coordinate system^{55,56}. Obviously, the Earth is moving with respect to this system and its motion can be measured, for example, using observations of the cosmic microwave background (CMB). The CMB radiation fills the cosmic space uniformly and isotopically in all directions except for a dipole anisotropy^{1-3,35,49}. This CMB perturbation is produced by the Doppler effect connected to the motion of the Earth and our Galaxy in cosmic space^{9,10}. Analysing the dipole anisotropy in the CMB, the drift,

undetectable by the Michelson-Morley experiments, can be successfully measured.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

No new data were generated or analysed in support of this research.

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